

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS ON THE BEARING CAPACITY OF SANDWICH PANEL JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

Sandwich panels as façade elements are preferred elements in the building industry. They consist of two metal sheets which enclose a rigid core of insulating material (for example polyurethane foam or mineral wool). The combination of load transfer and insulation, the ease of installation and the homogenous surface make them popular with engineers and architects alike.

Besides the many advantages of sandwich panels, a detractor in comparison to trapezoidal profiles is the need for additional structural elements. While a shear field of trapezoidal profiles may be used to stabilize attached beams or to brace the construction itself, a building envelope made of sandwich panels is only considered as a self-supporting element. The panels provide wind and snow load transfer to the substructure; however, they are currently not permissible according to industry standards for the full stabilization or bracing of the steel structure.

With regard to this problem, possible solutions have been assessed at the Institute of Steel Structures and Materials Mechanics at the TU Darmstadt. The goal of this research project is to reduce the necessary additional structural elements to a minimum and to gain the maximum stabilization effect provided by the diaphragm action of the sandwich panels. Within the scope of the experiments, the diaphragm action of sandwich panels has been tested on a shear frame rig with dimensions of up to 6 m x 6 m. The effect of parameters such as the dimensions, connection and joint design has been assessed. It has been found that the joint is a key factor for shear stiffness and bearing capacity. The bearing capacity itself has been increased by an order of magnitude by joint reinforcement.

1 INTRODUCTION

The goal of this research project is to minimize the necessary additional structural elements and to gain the maximum stabilisation effect provided by the diaphragm action of the sandwich panels. To this end, the effects of parameters such as the dimensions, connection and joint design need to be assessed. In this paper, the experimental setup (Figure 1), including the newly built shear frame rig and newly developed test set up for longitudinal joints is presented.

Figure 1: Shear frame rig with six sandwich panels

The results of the first diaphragm action tests series indicate that the connection between panel and beam is currently the limiting factor and that the strengthening of the joints would improve the bearing capacity of the shear field. The influence of the joints is subsequently assessed, modifications are proposed and tested. The aim of the tests carried out is to show the effect of the shear diaphragm action of sandwich panels. The panels were tested on a shear frame rig with dimensions of up to 6 m x 6 m, which is shown in Figure 1. Each panel has a cross section like the one pictured in Figure 2. The results were compared to theoretical considerations based on the European Recommendations on the Stabilisation of Steel Structures by Sandwich Panels.

Figure 2: Cross section of a sandwich panel

2 THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS AND CALCULATION MODEL

The determination of the shear stiffness S is described in the European Recommendations on the Stabilisation of Steel Structures by Sandwich Panels [1] for unidirectional spanning panels, which have no connections at the longitudinal edges. The equation (1) can be used to calculate the shear stiffness S . In Figure 3 the adjustment of the panels is shown. For each panel the position of P is marked. This is the point the panels rotate around due to the force F . Figure 4 shows the displacement of the fastenings, when the panels move.

$$S = \frac{k_v}{2 \cdot L} \cdot n \cdot m \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{n_k} c_k^2 \quad (1)$$

Where	k_v	stiffness of the fastenings (according to 3.3 [1])
	n	number of sandwich panels
	m	number of beams to be stabilised
	n_k	number of pairs of fasteners per panel and support
	c_k	distance between the two fasteners of a pair

Figure 3: Displacement of shear loaded unidirectionally spanning sandwich panels [1]

Figure 4: Displacement of fastenings [1]

The calculation model considers the stiffness of the fastenings and acts on the assumption that the panels are not connected to the substructure at the longitudinal edges. The stiffness of the longitudinal joints is neglected, which leads to an independent deformation of each sandwich panel. Each pair of self-drilling screws, depicted in Figure 4, can bear a moment of inertia, which counteracts the rotation of the sandwich panel. The calculation model does not include the stiffness of the longitudinal joints of the sandwich panels between one another. The joint is commonly designed as a tongue and groove connection with no load bearing function. Nevertheless the joint's stiffness might provide an improvement of the bearing capacity of the structure. This effect is tested on the shear frame rig presented in the following section.

3 SHEAR FRAME RIG

3.1 Experimental setup of the rig

The shear frame rig, which is shown in Figure 5, consists of two HEB 260 beams (A&B) and two HEB 140 beams (C&D). The beams are pin-jointed and the wheel mounted rig is freely movable. One of the larger beams (B) has a rigid connection to the floor and supports the structure. During the testing the other HEB 260 (A) is moved parallel to the rigid beam with the help of a hydraulic jack (E). The hydraulic jack (E) is placed horizontally besides the rig. One of the smaller beams (D) can be placed on different position on the larger beams (A&B). This allows shear field dimensions of 6 m x 6 m (six sandwich panels), 6 m x 3 m (three sandwich panels) or 6 m x 1 m (one sandwich panel).

Figure 5: Shear frame rig

The four-hinged frame was braced by sandwich panels as can be seen in Figure 1. The panels have a length of 6000 mm and are 1000 mm wide. Six of these panels represent an approximately 6 x 6 m shear field. The sandwich panels are connected to the shear frame rig by self-drilling screws. Square tubes with a thickness of 4 mm are welded on to the upper flange of the I-beams and serve as the substructure of the screws. The number of screws on each short side of the panels is defined by the distance of the panel lines. A screw is fastened in every second valley, which leads to a distance of 175 mm between the screws and a number of 6 screws per side. The longitudinal side of the outer panels was also connected to the substructure by 29 screws with a distance of 200 mm. The different tests with the corresponding parameters are listed in Table 1.

Test N°	Number of panels	Panel thickness (mm)	Number of screws on the longitudinal side	Number of screws on the front side
1	6	60	2 x 29	6 x 6
2	6	60	2 x 29	6 x 6
3	6	80	2 x 29	6 x 6
4	6	100	2 x 29	6 x 6
5	3	80	2 x 29	3 x 6
6	1	100	1 x 29	1 x 6
7	1	100	-	1 x 6
8	1	80	-	1 x 6

Table 1: Tests on the shear frame rig

During the tests each panel rotates about a point, which is defined by the assembly of the screws. The panels slide parallel to each other because there are no connections in the longitudinal joints as can be recognised in Figure 7. The opposing resulting tilt of the self-drilling screws is shown in Figure 6. A more detailed image of a single screw is given in Figure 8.

Figure 7: Rotation of the panels

Figure 6: Pair of oppositely tilting screws

Figure 8: Tilting of the self-drilling screws

3.2 Test results (shear frame rig)

The experimental results of test 1 to 4 are given in Figure 9. Even though the panels used in the tests have three different thicknesses, the force displacement curves show the same characteristics and differ only after large displacements were reached in the tests. At the beginning the structure is quite stiff until the point when the hole elongation at the screws starts to increase rapidly. The rise in the end of the curves which starts at a displacement of roughly 300 mm can be explained by the tilting of the fasteners, when the screws are then tensile-loaded. At the end the tests were stopped due to the large displacements and because some of the fasteners were pulled through the thin face sheet. Thus the load decrease at the end is not caused by the structure.

Figure 9: Shear Diaphragm Action - 6 Panels (Length 6 m)

Bearing in mind that the extremely large displacements which occurred in the tests are not desirable, the first part up to 50 mm displacement is shown in a larger scale in Figure 10. The curves are qualitatively and even quantitatively similar, in particular when the large discrepancies such as the adjustment of the shear frame rig, the position of the fasteners and installation of the panels, which influence the test results, are taken into account.

Figure 10: Shear Diaphragm Action - 6 Panels (Length 6 m)

In the first four tests, six panels were placed on the shear frame. Afterwards the experimental setup was reduced to three panels. Then three tests were carried out with single sandwich panels. Test number 6 and 7 were performed on a sandwich panel with a thickness of 100 mm. These are the same kind of sandwich panels as the ones use in test number 4. The panel of test number six was connected to the substructure with six self-drilling screws on each of the two short front sides. This way of fastening the panel to the substructure represents a panel which is in one of the centre positions of test number 4. The panel in test number 7 was additionally fixed on one of the longitudinal sides with 29 self-drilling screws. This is the same type of fixing as the outer panels of test 4.

Theoretically test number 4 consisting of six panels should have the same load bearing capacity as the sum of four times test number 6 and two times test number 7 (based on [1]). This theoretical idea is depicted in Figure 11. However, the diagram shows that this assumption cannot be verified. The test with six panels connected among one another by longitudinal tongue and groove joints provides higher bearing capacity for the shear frame rig than the simple summation of the single panel tests. This leads to the question why it is not possible to add up the bearing capacity of the single panels, which are fastened in the same way as the panels in the assembly. This is deemed to be due to the longitudinal joints, the load bearing behaviour of which is neglected in every existing calculation model for shear diaphragm action.

Figure 11: Combination of the different tests

4 LONGITUDINAL JOINTS

The shear stiffness of the structure is increased by the inclusion of the bearing capacity of the longitudinal joints. The tongue and groove joint works against the rotation and displacement of the sandwich panels. The sandwich panels work as a unit and not as individual elements, which move around separate rotation points.

In the following tests on longitudinal joints a central sandwich panel was flanked by two others and a clamping force was applied. The load necessary to press the test body downwards was determined. Afterwards the joint was reinforced to gain a higher bearable load.

4.1 Test specimen (longitudinal joints)

The tests of the longitudinal joints were performed on various joint executions. In Figure 12 two of the investigated geometries are displayed. One major difference is the sealing in tape in “type a”. The transferable load between the panels depends mainly on the materials of the contact surfaces and the clamping force, which is further described in the following section.

a) Longitudinal joint with sealing tape

b) Longitudinal joint with a corrugated core

Figure 12: Design of the longitudinal joint

4.2 Experimental Setup (longitudinal joints)

The experimental test setup shown in Figure 13 consists of three sandwich panel parts. One panel has been cut in half to position the tongue part of the joint on one side and the groove section on the other side. Between these two 1.0 m long panel parts, which are placed at the sides of the experimental setup, the third test body is placed. This middle panel is 0.5 m long and is pressed downwards with the help of the hydraulic jack in the centre of the test specimen. A defined clamping force is applied by another hydraulic jack, which is arranged horizontally beside the sandwich panels. It can be seen on the right hand side of Figure 13. The horizontal force is measured on the left side to ensure that the clamping force is lead through the two joints into to the opposite support.

Figure 13: Experimental setup for the tests on longitudinal joints

In addition to the two hydraulic forces, the displacement in the centre of the middle panel is measured and the relative displacement between the side elements and the centre panel is also determined with the help of two displacement transducers. The measurement of the relative displacement is used to verify that the inner sandwich panel moves evenly without an undesired rotation. The resulting displacement between the edge of the middle panel and the tongue of the neighbouring part is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Longitudinal joint with sealing tape during testing

Tests were performed to determine the forced required to displace the middle panel downwards by 15 mm for four different clamping force steps. The first three tests on one assembly of sandwich panels have a clamping force of 0.5 kN. Thereafter, tests with clamping forces of 1.0 kN, 1.5 kN and finally 2.0 kN were performed. For each step three tests have been carried out.

4.3 Test results (longitudinal joints)

For every set up of sandwich panels three tests in each of the four load steps were performed. Figure 15 shows the test results of a longitudinal joint with sealing tape (“type a” as pictured in Figure 12 a). Due to the soft sealing tape between the neighbouring panels the curves have a smooth decrease in gradient after a high load increase at the beginning. As expected the construction is capable of bearing higher loads, if a bigger horizontal clamping force is introduced into the system.

After approximately 6 mm the load starts approaching the sliding frictional force. Once this is achieved the force resisting the motion of the central panel along its neighbours is no longer increased. The average values based on the three tests per load step are given in Table 2 row three. The clamping forces were set manually, could not be defined very accurately and decreased with time. In order to take these effects into account the actual clamping forces which were effective after a deflection of the middle panel of 15 mm are given in row two of Table 2.

Nominal clamping force	(kN)	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0
Actual clamping force	(kN)	0.39	0.84	1.24	1.66
Average threshold value of frictional force	(kN)	0.95	1.80	2.35	2.70

Table 2: Results of joint type a

Figure 15: Joint type a

The sliding friction force is independent of the size of the contact area and depends on the coefficient of sliding friction. This coefficient is related to the materials, which are in contact with one another. The fact that the threshold values for the different load steps are not linearly related shows that the coefficient of sliding friction changes. This might be due to the compression of the sealing tape. However, similar joints with different heights do not have the same coefficient of sliding friction, because of the proportion between the part of the joint where the surface consists of steel and the part where the surface is the sealing tape changes.

The tests on longitudinal joints with a corrugated core, where the polyurethane foam meets directly with the polyurethane foam of the neighbour panel, have a different outcome as depicted in Figure 16. The curves have a high inclination at the beginning and after approximately 2 mm the load does not increase anymore. After a small decrease the load reaches an almost constant value. This is the force which is needed to slide the panels parallel to each other. The constant load after a certain displacement can also be seen in Figure 15 but not the load peak.

The average threshold values of the sliding friction force are almost linear to the increase of the clamping force. The coefficient of sliding friction of the polyurethane contact area is approximately $\mu = 0.8$.

Nominal clamping force	(kN)	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0
Actual clamping force	(kN)	0.47	0.92	1.38	1.87
Average threshold value of frictional force	(kN)	0.75	1.45	2.20	2.65

Table 3: Results of joint type b

Figure 16: Joint type b

5 STRENGTHENING OF THE LONGITUDINAL JOINT

5.1 Possible reinforcement methods

The next step was to improve the bearing capacity of the longitudinal joint. Different approaches were tested, two of which are presented in the following section. In case of the reinforced set up a horizontal clamping force of 0.5 kN was applied. Figure 17 shows a joint which is glued together by a 1-component polyurethane prepolymer adhesive. The adhesive bonds very well with the rigid polyurethane foam and after a rather short curing time the joint presents a very solid connection.

Figure 17: Longitudinal Joint with 1-component polyurethane prepolymer adhesive

Another idea is to strengthen the tongue and groove connection by using hook-and-loop tape (Figure 18). The tape was glued on to the rigid core material with the 1-component polyurethane prepolymer adhesive used before. The advantages of the hook-and-loop tape are the facts that the connection is detachable without destroying the joint and that no gluing on the construction site is necessary. According to the producer the hook-and-loop tape can be opened and closed up to 10 000 times.

a) Top view of the joint

b) Side face of the joint

Figure 18: Longitudinal Joint with Hook-and-Loop tape

5.2 Test results of the reinforced longitudinal joint

The tests on the strengthened longitudinal joints show good results with a significantly augmented bearing capacity (Figure 19). The stiffness of the connection is higher and the joint is not the weakest part of the structure anymore. In case of the glued connection the stiffness of the joint is higher than the one of the hook-and-loop tape. In both methods of reinforcement, the failure mode is the breaking of the polyurethane foam itself as shown in Figure 20. The bearing capacity is increased by more than an order of magnitude.

Figure 19: Joints with reinforcement methods

a) Glued joint (top view)

b) Glued joint
(side view)

c) Hook-and-loop tape

Figure 20: Failure of the reinforced longitudinal joints

6 CONCLUSIONS

Including the stiffness of the longitudinal joint into the calculation model for the shear stiffness of sandwich panel diaphragms can provide better values for the cladding. To implement it into the model it is necessary to provide a reliable value for the stiffness of the joint. Reinforcement of the longitudinal joint not only significantly increases its shear stiffness, but also offers a more dependable prediction of the expected bearing capacity. The bearing capacity itself is increased by an order of magnitude.

REFERENCES

- [1] Technical Working Group 7.9, CIB Working Commission W056 “European recommendations on the stabilisation of steel structures by sandwich panels”, 2014.